

Volumetric and viscometric studies of copper(II) surfactant derived from four edible oils in methanol-benzene mixture

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Abstract : The density and viscosity of copper(II) soaps derived from four edible oils (mustard, groundnut, sesame and soyabean) in non-aqueous solvents of varying composition has been determined at constant temperature. The results were used to determine the critical micelle concentration (cmc), soap-solvent interactions and the effect of the chain length of the soap molecules on various parameters. The cmc values in higher volume percent of methanol are higher than those in higher volume percent of benzene, with regard to chain length of the soap cmc value follows the order :

CSo > CSe > CG > CM

The conclusions with regard to soap-soap and soap-solvent interactions have been discussed in terms of well known Masson's and Jones-Dole equations. These vital information play an important role in their selection for various industrial and biological applications.

Keywords : Copper(II) soaps, edible oils, molar volume, viscosity.

Introduction

Copper soaps derived from four edible oils provide an interesting area of investigation pertaining to its fundamental information regarding their colloidal-chemical behaviour¹⁻³. Copper(II) soaps in polar and non-polar solvents have gained considerable popularity, due to their immense use and widespread applications such as wood preservation, foaming, wetting, biocidal, pesticidal activities, detergency, emulsification, paints, lubrications etc.⁴⁻⁷. All these applications led us to study micellar features of copper soaps derived from four edible oils for their possible uses and applications in agriculture and industries.

The present work deals with the study of density and viscosity of copper soaps derived from four edible oils in a ternary system. Molar volume and apparent molar volume ϕ_v have been measured from density data in order to find cmc, nature and size of the micelles formed in non-aqueous media^{8,9}. The apparent molar volume and partial molar volume data for non-electrolyte have been used to obtain information regarding solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions, whereas the effect of soap concentra-

tion on viscosity of soap solution in polar and non-polar solvent has been discussed in terms of Jones-Dole equation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of LR/AR grade. Solvent was purified according to standard procedure before use¹⁰. Oils were procured directly from the seeds of mustard, groundnut and sesame. Soyabean (pure) oil was taken from the market of a reputed brand. Copper soap was prepared by refluxing the edible oils with alcohol and 2 N KOH solution for 3 h (direct metathesis). The neutralization of excess of KOH present was done by 1 N HCl. Saturated solution of copper sulphate was then added to it for conversion of neutralized soap into copper soap. Copper soap so obtained was then washed with hot water and dried. The soap was recrystallized using hot benzene. The fatty acid composition of these edible oils were confirmed through GLC of their methyl ester and is given in Table 1. The formation of copper soap was confirmed by using UV, IR techniques and elemental analysis. The purity of soap was confirmed by TLC.

Table 1. Fatty acid composition of oils used for copper soap synthesis

Name of oil	% Fatty acids					Other acids
	16 : 0	18 : 0	18 : 1	18 : 2	18 : 3	
Mustard oil	2	1	25	18	10	C ₂₀ -C ₂₂ 41%
Groundnut oil	10	4	61	18	-	C ₂₀ -C ₂₄ 7%
Sesame oil	8	4	5	41	-	-
Soyabean oil	12	4	24	51	9	-

Ostwald modification of the springel pycnometer with a volume of about 15 ml, which allowed an accuracy of about one unit in the fourth place of decimal was used for measuring the density of the soap solution in a thermostated water bath at 303 K ($\pm 0.1\%$ accuracy). An Ostwald's viscometer was used to determine the viscosity of the soap solutions in a thermostatic water bath. The viscometer was calibrated frequently with distilled water. The accuracy of the results was checked by determining the viscosity of known solutions. The agreement was found to be good and difference was below 0.3%. All solutions were made by weight and vacuum correction done for weighting. In all cases precautions were taken to prevent evaporation of the solvent.

Results and discussion

The copper soaps derived from four edible oils in 20% and 40% methanol-benzene mixture are abbreviated as follow :

- | | | |
|----------------------------|-------------------|-------------------|
| (i) Copper mustard soap | CM ₂₀ | CM ₄₀ |
| (ii) Copper groundnut soap | CG ₂₀ | CG ₄₀ |
| (iii) Copper sesame soap | CSe ₂₀ | CSe ₄₀ |
| (iv) Copper soyabean soap | CSo ₂₀ | CSo ₄₀ |

The apparent molar volume has been calculated with the error limit of $\pm 0.2\%$ from the density using the following equations.

$$\phi_v = \frac{M}{\rho_0} + 1000 \frac{(\rho_0 - \rho)}{c \cdot \rho_0} \quad (1)$$

where M , ρ , ρ_0 and c (g mol/L) are the molecular weights of the soaps, the density of the solution, density of the solvent and the concentration of solution respectively.

Density and apparent molar volume :

The density of copper soaps derived from four edible

oils (CM, CG, CSe and CSo) in 20% methanol-benzene mixture are higher than that of 40% methanol-benzene mixture and follows the order (Tables 2-5).

$$CSo > CSe > CG > CM$$

Which is due to the fact that the density increases with the increase in the shorter fatty acid content in the corresponding oil composition. The cmc of soaps obtained from density vs conc. plots follows the order :

$$CSo > CSe > CG > CM$$

This observation is in agreement with the fact that there is a decrease in cmc values with the increase of the average molecular weight of the soap and presence of longer fatty acid content in oil composition¹².

According to our observation ϕ_v values for copper soap in both the solvent mixture are negative. Their negative values could be ascribed on the basis of group additivity, which shows that different groups will display increasingly negative value according to their increasing polarity and hydrogen bonding capabilities. The plots of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} are characterized by an intersection of curve and a straight line, in each case which corresponds to the cmc of the soap (Fig. 1). The value of apparent molar volume of CG and CSo increases sharply below cmc. In CM a convex curve with respect to X-axis is observed below cmc. Above cmc the ϕ_v value decreases gradually with increase in concentration, while for CSe the value of ϕ_v decrease below cmc and after cmc the ϕ_v value increase with increase in soap conc. The cmc obtained from the plots ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} also follow the same order as for density and molar volume (Table 6). cmc obtained in this study is also confirmed by other physical properties like viscosity and ultrasonic velocity. This is in agreement with the observation that there is decrease in cmc value with the increase in the average molecular weight of the soaps¹³.

The data has been analyzed in terms of Masson equation¹⁴.

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad (2)$$

The values of limiting apparent molar volume ϕ_v^0 and constant S_v are a measure of solute-solvent and solute-solute interaction respectively (Table 7).

As Masson equation fits well for above cmc in all the copper soap in 20% and 40% methanol-benzene mixture.

Table 2. Density, apparent molar volume and viscosity of copper mustard soap in methanol-benzene mixture at constant temperature (303 + 0.1 K)

Soap conc. (g mol L ⁻¹)	Density (g/cm ³)		A.M.V (Φ _v)		Viscosity (milli poise) (η)		Specific viscosity (η _{sp})	
	20	40	20	40	20	40	20	40
0.0003	0.8588	0.8423	-2343.3	-4270.4	5.8188	5.9018	0.01730	0.00741
0.0004	0.8590	0.8427	-2149.1	-4173.3	5.8669	5.9390	0.02570	0.01376
0.0006	0.8595	0.8434	-2149.1	-3881.9	5.9522	6.0128	0.04060	0.02636
0.0008	0.8599	0.8440	-2003.4	-3590.5	6.0485	6.0630	0.05740	0.03493
0.0010	0.8601	0.8444	-1624.6	-3205.9	6.1315	6.1465	0.07190	0.04917
0.0011	0.8599	0.8440	-1210.7	-2345.5	6.2004	6.1775	0.08400	0.05447
0.0012	0.8600	0.8437	-1177.8	-1842.3	6.2201	6.1986	0.08740	0.05807
0.0013	0.8603	0.8441	-1297.4	-1999.2	6.2503	6.2360	0.09270	0.06446
0.0014	0.8606	0.8444	-1399.8	-2050.4	6.2806	6.2497	0.09800	0.06679
0.0016	0.8610	0.8451	-1420.7	-2206.5	6.3023	6.3009	0.10180	0.07553
0.0018	0.8615	0.8458	-1501.6	-2327.9	6.3411	6.3521	0.10860	0.08428
0.0020	0.8620	0.8464	-1566.3	-2366.7	6.4034	6.4027	0.11950	0.09291

Table 3. Density, apparent molar volume and viscosity of copper groundnut soap in methanol-benzene mixture at constant temperature (303 ± 0.1 K)

Soap conc. (g mol L ⁻¹)	Density (g/cm ³)		A.M.V (Φ _v)		Viscosity (milli poise) (η)		Specific viscosity (η _{sp})	
	20	40	20	40	20	40	20	40
0.0003	0.8587	0.8422	-19040	-3924.2	5.7480	5.8782	0.00490	0.00340
0.0004	0.8590	0.8428	-20980	-4518.8	5.7968	5.9168	0.01342	0.01000
0.0006	0.8595	0.8438	-20980	-47060	5.8236	5.9800	0.01810	0.02080
0.0008	0.8600	0.8445	-20980	-4370.1	5.8503	6.0551	0.02279	0.03360
0.0010	0.8602	0.8441	-17486	-2866.0	5.8985	6.1212	0.03121	0.04490
0.0011	0.8604	0.8440	-17510	-2410.9	6.0405	6.1664	0.05603	0.05260
0.0012	0.8607	0.8444	-17590	-25370	6.0890	6.1923	0.06450	0.05700
0.0013	0.8609	0.8447	-1784.4	-2552.2	6.1376	6.2060	0.07300	0.05930
0.0014	0.8611	0.8451	-17910	-2650.2	6.2095	6.2549	0.08558	0.06700
0.0016	0.8616	0.8459	-17950	-2809.5	6.2831	6.3068	0.09845	0.07650
0.0018	0.8620	0.8466	-18010	-2867.3	3.3334	6.3500	0.10723	0.08390
0.0020	0.8625	0.8474	-18320	-29730	6.4544	6.3987	0.12839	0.09220

Table 4. Density, apparent molar volume and viscosity of copper sesame soap in methanol-benzene mixture at constant temperature (303 ± 0.1 K)

Soap conc. (g mol L ⁻¹)	Density (g/cm ³)		A.M.V (Φ _v)		Viscosity (milli poise) (η)		Specific viscosity (η _{sp})	
	20	40	20	40	20	40	20	40
0.0003	0.8589	0.8424	-2742.7	-4669.9	5.8429	5.9140	0.02150	0.00949
0.0004	0.8593	0.8426	-3034.1	-3892.9	5.8807	5.9613	0.02810	0.01756
0.0006	0.8600	0.8432	-3131.2	-3504.4	5.9790	6.0573	0.04530	0.03395
0.0008	0.8608	0.8438	-3325.4	-3310.2	6.0666	6.1879	0.06060	0.05624

Table-4 (contd.)

0.0010	0.8616	0.8445	-3420.4	-3310.2	6.1306	6.2390	0.07180	0.06496
0.0011	0.8620	0.8448	-3442.4	-3257.2	6.2038	6.2872	0.08460	0.07319
0.0012	0.8624	0.8450	-3490.5	-3115.9	6.2536	6.3231	0.09330	0.07933
0.0013	0.8624	0.8452	-3191.0	-3119.0	6.2773	6.3708	0.09740	0.08747
0.0014	0.8625	0.8454	-2992.4	-2893.9	6.3015	6.4181	0.10170	0.09554
0.0016	0.8627	0.8457	-2669.8	-2654.6	6.3499	6.4664	0.11010	0.10379
0.0018	0.8630	0.8460	-2483.7	-2468.4	6.3991	6.5033	0.11870	0.11008
0.0020	0.8635	0.8463	-2451.3	-2319.5	6.4498	6.5516	0.12760	0.11833

Table 5. Density, apparent molar volume and viscosity of copper soyabean soap in methanol-benzene mixture at constant temperature (303+0.1 K)

Soap conc. (g mol L ⁻¹)	(Volume % of methanol in solvent mixture)							
	Density (g/cm ³)		A.M.V (ϕ_v)		Viscosity (milli poise) (η)		Specific viscosity (η_{sp})	
	20	40	20	40	20	40	20	40
0.0003	0.8591	0.8425	-3530.9	-5069.9	5.8793	5.9789	0.02785	0.02057
0.0004	0.8595	0.8428	-3484.8	-4487.1	5.9401	6.0544	0.03849	0.03346
0.0006	0.8601	0.8433	-3294.8	-3710.1	6.0381	6.1268	0.05561	0.04582
0.0008	0.8604	0.8437	-2824.8	-3175.9	6.1461	6.2216	0.07449	0.06499
0.0010	0.8608	0.8441	-2520.8	-2855.4	6.2423	6.3279	0.09130	0.08014
0.0011	0.8610	0.8444	-2436.0	-2844.8	6.3023	6.3646	0.00180	0.08640
0.0012	0.8612	0.8446	-2365.4	-2738.9	6.3623	6.4075	0.11230	0.09372
0.0013	0.8608	0.8443	-1767.7	-2200.9	6.4062	6.4557	0.11997	0.10196
0.0014	0.8613	0.8438	-2004.6	-1573.4	6.4451	6.5093	0.12677	0.11111
0.0016	0.8619	0.8449	-2098.3	-2083.3	6.5082	6.5868	0.13780	0.12433
0.0018	0.8627	0.8460	-2300.6	-2479.9	6.5495	6.6299	0.14501	0.13169
0.0020	0.8633	0.8468	-2346.0	-2622.3	6.6010	6.6592	0.15402	0.13669

While for CG, CSe and CSo below cmc due to presence of curvature nature is applicable only at the initial part of the curve consisting dilute concentration range for all the copper soap solute-solvent interaction follows the order :

$$\phi_{v_2}^0 > \phi_{v_1}^0 \text{ and } \phi_v(20\%) > \phi_v(40\%)$$

The data also reveals that solute-solvent interactions decreases with the increase in the chain length of the soap segment above cmc for both the solvent mixture (Table 7).

$$\phi_{v_2}^0(\text{CSo}) > \phi_{v_1}^0(\text{CM})$$

The parameter S_v in Masson's equation represents the limiting apparent slope and indicates the existence of solute-solute interactions. The values of S_v in both the solvent mixture follows the order :

$$S_{v_1}(40\%) > S_{v_1}(20\%)$$

$$S_{v_2}(20\%) > S_{v_2}(40\%)$$

The data clearly indicates that solute-solute interactions increases with the predominance of polar solvent in the solvent mixture (Table 7).

Viscosity (η , milli poise) fluidity ϕ and specific viscosity (η_{sp}) are considered to be important rheological parameters. The viscosity of the copper soap derived from four edible oils in methanol-benzene mixture increases with increasing soap concentration (Tables 2-5). The increase in viscosity with the increase in soap concentration may be due to the increasing tendency of copper soap molecules to form aggregates in the form of micelles. The existence of micelles of surfactants in organic solvents and mixed solvents have been reported by number of workers¹⁵⁻¹⁹. Viscosity of copper soap in 40% methanol-benzene mixture is slightly higher than that of 20% methanol-benzene mixture which is due to the difference in the viscosities of solvent mixture.

Fig. 1. Plots of apparent molar volume vs square root of concentration of copper soaps derived from various edible oils in 20% methanol-benzene mixture : (•) CM, (□) CG, (▲) CSe, (●) CSo.

Table 6. Value of cmc of copper soaps derived from four edible oils in 20% and 40% methanol-benzene mixture

Volume % →	20%				40%			
Plots ↓	CM	CG	CSe	CSo	CM	CG	CSe	CSo
d vs C	0.0010	0.0011	0.0012	0.0013	0.0011	0.0012	0.0013	0.0014
ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C}	0.0009	0.0011	0.0012	0.0014	0.0011	0.0012	0.0013	0.0014
η vs C	0.0010	0.0011	0.0012	0.0013	0.0011	0.0012	0.0013	0.0014
η_{sp} vs \sqrt{C}	0.0010	0.0011	0.0012	0.0013	0.0011	0.0012	0.0013	0.0014
$\psi/\Delta C$ vs \sqrt{C}	0.0010	0.0011	0.0012	0.0013	0.0011	0.0012	0.0013	0.0014

Table 7. Computed parameters of Masson equation and viscosity parameters of Jones-Dole equation for copper soaps derived from four edible oils in methanol-benzene mixture

Name of the soap	ϕ_{v_1}	ϕ_{v_2}	S_{v_1}	S_{v_2}	A_1	A_2	B_1	B_2
CM	-	-16.4	-	-0.1051	0.42	2.180	0.5773	2.3558
CG	-25.6	-5.0	+0.5773	-0.6745	0.72	2.200	1.7320	0.3249
CSe	-27.3	-60.0	-0.6008	+2.7474	1.16	2.380	1.4825	0.3443
CSo	-38.5	+2.0	+1.5398	-1.6003	1.54	3.000	1.7320	0.3639
CM	-	-13.2	-	-0.4244	0.12	0.700	1.7320	0.8390
CG	-47.2	-1.00	+0.6248	-0.4452	0.22	0.980	0.6248	0.3443
CSe	-58.2	-59.4	-1.3763	+1.0355	0.38	1.870	1.9626	0.4877
CSo	-51.5	+25.0	+1.7320	-1.8807	0.94	2.000	0.8390	0.4040

Fig. 2. Plots of viscosity vs soap concentration of copper soaps derived from various edible oils in 20% methanol-benzene mixture : (♦) CM, (□) CG, (▲) CSe, (●) CSo.

Fig. 3. Plots of viscosity of η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} of copper soaps derived from various edible oils in 20% methanol-benzene mixture (Jones-Dole equation) : (□) CG, (▲) CSe, (●) CSo.

The plots of viscosity (η) against soap concentration are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines corresponding to cmc of the soap (Fig. 2). The increase

in viscosity above the cmc may be attributed to the fact that the aggregation of the soap molecules boosts up electro-kinetic forces, causing more intake of the solvent

Fig. 4. Plot of viscosity of η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} of copper soaps derived from various edible oils in 40% methanol-benzene mixture (Jones-Dole equation) : (●) CM, (◆) CSo.

and resulting in increased viscosity of the system. The values of cmc are recorded in Table 6 and follows the order :

$$CSo > CSe > CG > CM$$

This is an agreement with the fact that there is a decrease in the cmc values with the increase in the number of carbon atom in the hydrophobic chain²⁰.

The values of specific viscosity (η_{sp}) of copper soap derived from four edible oils solutions in varying composition of methanol-benzene mixtures also increase with the increase in the soap concentration. The nature of curve and cmc values are in good agreement with those observed for viscosity data. The fluidity (ϕ) of copper soap solutions in methanol-benzene mixtures decreases with the increase in the soap concentration as well as with the increase in volume percent of benzene. A perusal of Table 7 indicates that cmc values are in good agreement with those obtained from viscosity, specific viscosity and fluidity.

Further viscosity data have been analysed in the light of Jones-Dole equation²¹.

$$\frac{(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)}{\sqrt{C}} = A + B \sqrt{C}$$

For convenience, the equation may be expressed as

$$\frac{\psi}{\sqrt{C}} = A + B \sqrt{C}$$

where the coefficients A and B refer to solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions respectively. The plots ψ/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} are characterised by intersection of two straight lines at a point corresponding to the cmc of the soap (Figs. 3, 4). The values of cmc are in good agreement with the values derived from the plots of η , η_{sp} and ϕ vs C (Table 6). In view of the two intersecting straight lines for ψ/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} plots, it is reasonable to evaluate two values of each coefficient below and above cmc designated as A_1 , B_1 and A_2 , B_2 respectively (Table 7).

It is obvious from the Table 7 that the values of constant A (solute-solute interactions) are smaller than the values of constant B (solute-solvent) interactions, which confirms that copper soap molecules do not aggregate appreciably below cmc while there is sudden change in the aggregation above cmc. Further A_1 and A_2 (solute-solute) interaction in 20% methanol-benzene mixture are found higher than 40% methanol-benzene mixture. This may be accounted in terms of a change in the mobility of

the solute with a change in the dielectric constant of the medium²². It is observed that the values of constant B_1 for the copper soap derived from four edible oils in various composition of solvent are higher suggesting the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions.

The values of constant B also increases with the increasing concentration of benzene in the solvent mixture. A perusal of Table 7 shows that there is large difference in the positive values of B_1 and B_2 , which is in conformity with the observation that B is always positive in non-aqueous media²³. Positive value of B indicates a strong alignment of solvent molecules with solute, which reveals the structure forming behaviour of the solvent, decrease in B values. The trend of coefficients may thus be summed up as :

$$A_2 > A_1 \text{ and } B_1 > B_2$$

$$A_1, A_2 (20\%) > A_1, A_2 (40\%)$$

$$B_1, B_2 (40\%) > B_1, B_2 (20\%)$$

on the basis of the results obtained it can finely be concluded that the above treatment gives satisfactory explanation of clustering profile and confirms the existence of soap aggregation non-aqueous mixed solvents. These studies has been supported by various workers^{24,25}.

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